

Liberal Democracy: Concepts for Economic Growth, Happiness, Human Rights, Religion and Decision of Death

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Abstract

How to address human rights is a forever important issue of political economics. In expanding that view, knowing whether the decision has a firm ground is essential. We, humans, say that every decision should be addressed from the rational point of view of human rights. And to support that, the economic rationale for the decision is essential.

That brings us to the question of what is a good decision. A good decision refers to a decision when making a decision in which a previous decision influences a subsequent decision with an economic benefit. Therefore, when exploring time-to-time decisions, the goal is to pattern laws for the types of decisions that occur in reality.

We will discuss the fundamental model ground for a good decision in an economic sense in this paper.

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1 About the Author

I was born on October 24, 1992, to my father Yoon In-deok and mother Chun Kyung-ah as the eldest son. After graduating from Samreung Elementary School, Sanghyeon Middle School, and Dongjak High School, I entered the Department of Oriental Medicine at Daejeon University in 2011, graduated from the Department of Oriental Medicine at Daejeon University in 2020, and obtained an oriental medicine license (license number 28216). I dedicate this book to my loving father and mother.

2 Introduction

In the universe, there is a pale blue dot[1] which is called mother earth. Humans live in time and space on mother earth, which is a great blessing. And on that earth, humans have developed a survival strategy called “economy”. We are writing this paper to give the answers to the essential questions that bring us to a strategy called “economy”. The economy is about making decisions. So we will talk about making decisions first. The economics of making strategic decisions is called “game theory”.

3 Decision - Game Theory

3.1 New approach to Game Theory

3.1.1 Construction of Game Theory

Game theory is a theory proposed for figuring out how to make the best decisions in-game moments. Although the name of the theory “Game” usually refers to the recreational activities, Game theory, in fact, focuses on not only recreational moments, but also every moment of interaction between the economical agents. It consists of elements related to the game’s rules, strategy, and results. The game’s rules relate to the players, the order of the match, and the knowledge and information known to the players during the game. Strategy is about actions that players can take at any point in time. Elements related to the result link to the utility that can be generated according to the players’ actions and the remuneration to be obtained by each player through the realization of the result. But game theory has limitations. Unlike the premise of game theory, humans do not assume the most rational situation for games every time. People try to maximize profits by minimizing irrational factors and maximizing reasonable factors. Through this, the premise of game theory can be summarized as follows[2].

1. Rule of the game

(a) Game participant

- In an ideal premise, game participants insist on rational judgments. But still, game participants in the real economy try to minimize irrational judgments to make rational judgments as much as possible.

(b) Game playing order

- In an ideal premise, whether a game is simultaneous or sequential is already determined. But in a real economy, the superiority or inferiority that can determine whether a game is simultaneous or sequential sometimes affects the game.

(c) Knowledge and information that a competitor knows during the game

- In an ideal premise, players focus on whether or not they can recall the details of the game, but in a real economy, the less information they have, the more errors they make before making sound decisions.
- In an ideal premise, the focus is on whether the decisions of game participants are disclosed, but in a real economy, any decision made can have various meanings.
- In an ideal premise, it is assumed that all premises of the situation are considered during the game, but in a real economy, greater marginal utility can be created due to what other game participants did not consider at the time of the game.

2. Strategy

(a) Action or strategy that a game player can take at every point in time

- In an ideal premise, it is assumed that game participants do their best in each game. But still, in a real economy, decisions are based on one-off opportunities rather than reasonable probability calculations.

3. Result factors

(a) Consequences of the participants' actions

- In an ideal premise, the expected utility hypothesis is followed, but in a real economy, people assume that they are rational and do not make the best decisions.

(b) Payment earned by individual competitors for the realization of the results

- In an ideal premise, it is assumed that the distribution of internal profits among game participants is the same, but in a real economy, when all members' choices are considered, there is always a difference in the distribution of internal profits among game participants.

Considering the difference between the ideal premise and the application of reality as above, market participants in the real economy consider the following selection characteristics.

1. Market participants minimize irrational judgments to maximize rational judgments.
2. Market participants will be affected by whether they play games simultaneously or sequentially.
3. The less market participants know about the market, the more mistakes they make before they make a sound decision.
4. Any decision can have multiple implications.
5. Larger marginal utility can be created due to what was not considered during the market transaction.
6. Market participants may prioritize a one-time opportunity over a transaction based on probability calculations.
7. Market participants may mistake themselves for rationality and make poor decisions.
8. Even if market participants try to make decisions with everyone in mind, there will always be internal differences in the distribution of benefits among market participants.

3.2 Application to the real economy

3.2.1 Two types of games and Determinants in the real economy

A strategic game is one in which a specific decision is made at a particular time. Based on No. 8 of the market participants' selection characteristics above, the law of the game environment is derived as follows.

- Decisions about time in the game affect differences in the distribution of internal benefits within individual game participants.
 - (Law of Time 1) Decisions made at the right time reduce distortions in the distribution of internal benefits within game participants.
- Decisions about the time during a game affect consensus among game participants.
 - (Law of Time 2) Decisions made at the right time suppress controversy over agreement on details of the game.

An extensive game means that specific decisions are made continuously in one space. Based on No. 2 of the market participants' selection characteristics above, the law of the game environment is derived as follows.

- Decisions about space affect the superiority and inferiority between the strong and the weak
 - (Law of Space 1) Each game player tries to advance the game in the most advantageous position for themselves.
- Decisions about space affect whether the strong and the weak consider superiority and inferiority
 - (Law of Space 2) The weak aim for the weakest point of the strong, and the strong prefer the place where their strengths are most evident as the game location.

Accordingly, the following factors may be adjusted in the progress of the game environment. And in a real economy, strategic and extensive games usually coincide. This can be applied as follows.

1. (Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 1) A game participant may interfere with the opponent's preferred game location to reduce the opponent's internal profit distribution.
 - Market participants may interfere with other market participants' preferred market choices to degrade the internal profit distribution of other market participants.
2. (Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 2) A game participant can lower the opponent's internal profit distribution by interfering with the opponent's selection of a preferred game location.
 - Market participants may undermine other market participants' favored market choices by lowering the internal profit distribution.
3. (Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 1) A game participant attempts to select and exclude a market favored by an opposing player based on the details of the game.

- A market participant attempts to select a market other than the one the other market participant favored based on game details.
4. (Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 2) Game participants hope that the details of the game will be decided, excluding the market preferred by the other participant.
- Market participants wish to specify game details for markets not favored by other participants.

The remaining six of the above laws can be classified as follows.

1. Fallacy of perception

- (No. 3) The fewer market participants know about the market, the more mistakes they make before they make a sound decision.
- (No. 7) Market participants may mistake themselves for rationality and make poor decisions.

2. Fallacy of memory

- (No. 4) Any decision can have multiple implications.
- (No. 5) Larger marginal utility can be created due to what was not considered during the market transaction.

3. Fallacy of opportunity

- (No. 1) Market participants minimize irrational judgments to maximize rational judgments.
- (No. 6) Market participants may prioritize a one-time opportunity over a transaction based on probability calculations.

This can be summarized as follows.

- Wrong perceptions, wrong memories, and wrong opportunities meet game participants and distort their choices in time and space. These make difference between competitors.

3.2.2 Concealment of reality with offering agreeable compromise

In the real world, strategies are constantly exposed to the opponents, with each game opportunity presented. Accordingly, the aspect of dispersing the predictability of the system by concealing the behavior appears. As a result, two error terms are induced, making it difficult for the game participants to conceive the process as much as possible.

1. Concealment of reality — Unclear recognition or exposure of strategic skills
2. Searching for reality — Clear recognition or exposure of strategic skills

This is an essential protection from the opponent of the game participant to read the strategy.

Meanwhile, presenting a compromise as an incentive to the game opponent is also possible. By submitting a goal in the first place, game participants, on the other side, can reduce their resource consumption and receive incentives through agreement. This is also an error term because the game can be ended while reducing the expected resource consumption.

When presenting a compromise for an agreement, two things should be considered. First, it is necessary to consider the utility of exerting maximum pressure on market participants. Second, market participants must actively consider what their counterpart market participants want. This is because each of the two negotiation situations can be expected.

1. The opposing participant may avoid negotiating until the end of the game even though the odds of winning are slim. In such cases, it is necessary to decide whether the game should be continued based on the utility of the negotiations.
2. Game participants may not give their opponents the same opportunities in the game. For this reason, game participants must first understand what the other person wants and decipher the situation. In other words, game participants must provide a minimum mutually agreeable point to other game participants.

Put another way, proposing a consensus is necessary to reduce the wastage of resources despite trying to cover up the action. So these two are error terms. To explain, the error term in linear regression in econometrics can be taken as an example. This has properties similar to MSE (Mean Squared Error).

This can also be interpreted as an external effect. However, error terms are only parts of the direct externalities. The actual overall externality is the sum of all market variables, such as market participants' fallacies of perceptions, memories, and opportunity concealment of reality and searching for truth, appearing as they interact.

In addition, we do not want to comment here on general competitive equilibria in supply and demand (cobweb theory, Walrasian balance, Marshallian equilibrium, etc.)^{[3][4]}. This is because the error term must be minimized in linear regression, but the error term is essential in this model concept. This model does not seek a balance that reduces the error term. This is because, most intuitively, even when a situation arises where overall utility seems to decrease, the strategy needs to be hidden so that overall utility increases or the correct market equilibrium can nevertheless be achieved.

As a result, the fallacy concept of concealment of action and presentation of consensus encompasses the general competitive equilibrium, taking into account externalities. This links the Coase Theorem's universal, natural situation (effective resource allocation without transaction costs when externalities occur) to the ideal situation (effective resource allocation despite transaction costs when externalities arise).

4 Space – Gap between regions

4.1 What makes the difference in space overcome?

4.1.1 Basic structure of regional and inter-regional economies

What has created economic differences between regions? This is a simple question, and most people already know the answer. We live in space and time. Accordingly, we have formed economic differences according to regions according to regional attributes, time attributes, and people's interests.

Regional attributes relate to the space in which we live. We live in an area that produces economic output. Therefore, our first question to survive through the characteristics of a region is, "What kind of economic output can be produced here?"

However, we not only produce economic outputs, we also consume them. Accordingly, our second question to survive through regional attributes becomes, “What kind of economic output can we consume here?”

Time attributes are about the time we spend. We produce economic outputs by using time. Accordingly, our third question to survive through regional details becomes, “When can we produce economic output here?”

However, similar to the above, we not only produce economic outputs, we also consume them. Accordingly, our fourth question to survive through regional attributes becomes “When can economic output be consumed here?”

And finally, as humans, we have the freedom to be free[5]. But freedom comes at a price[6]. So we pay the price for our freedom to live. In this aspect, humans have been racing to free themselves from the burden of paying the price of a transaction. And we call freedom in these relationships as prosperity[7]. Thus, the last question becomes “How can we become more prosperous than now?”

To pay the price for choices in this freedom, human has faced collaboration and dispute between regions to expand freedom from the region[8]. Again, the price for freedom is not free. But from this point of view, we know that there are two kinds of freedom for freedom. One is collaboration; the other is dispute.

The freedom to collaborate comes at a price of concession and compromise. And this usually results in a peaceful ending. On the other hand, the freedom to dispute comes at the cost of conflict. And this usually results in a catastrophic outcome.

So, why do regional disputes arise for freedom? Intuitively, there could be two cases. One is when arguments extend regional space rather than concessions and compromises. And there are other cases where restricted freedom expands despite the catastrophic cost of giving up peace.

But we know from history that disputes are temporary and even waste valuable resources. In this context, humans must collaborate rather than fight.

So why does collaboration happen for the sake of freedom? Intuitively, it would be the case that concessions and compromises extend regional space rather than conflict. Another situation is that keeping the peace prevents catastrophic consequences and expands regional autonomy.

There are two ways to collaborate for economic freedom. One is through co-operation, the other through competition[9].

Rationally, humans now know that there are two cooperative avenues for economic freedom. One is to integrate to produce or consume more diverse economic outputs. Another option is to combine to make or consume economic output more quickly.

On the other hand, we humans now know that there are two competing avenues for economic freedom. One is to compete to produce and consume more diverse economic outputs. Another option is to compete to produce or consume economic output faster.

4.1.2 Establishment of trade and transactions between foreign currencies

We have entered the 21st century and are currently living in the age of capitalism. Money is essential in capitalism. It started with the concept of payment guarantee for price[10]. And it is necessary to note that price is a measure of social utility in a periodic slice[11]. The method of payment guarantees consisted mainly of what humans believed to be of perpetual and enduring value. Historically, there was gold, silver, etc.[12].

With the advent of money, markets appeared. Money was used in the market. The belief in the universality and permanence of money made transactions between

people more convenient[13]. Thus, the existence of an appropriate currency brings about a reduction in transaction costs[14].

A market is a place where commodities are traded. There are three types of actors in the market. Consumers are subjects who share demand behavior. Suppliers are entities that share the act of supply[15]. Supervisors (usually governments) regulate markets, commodities, trade, and currencies[16].

After markets appeared, collaborations between markets appeared. Different spaces created different needs. Therefore, we can say that the market is a space where a specific transaction is made using a particular currency in a specific place.

Accordingly, the two kinds of collaborations were also reflected in the market. It is cooperation and competition. And since the market exists within space, it has regional characteristics. As a result, regional cooperation units and regional competition units are created.

In regional cooperation units, cooperation at the commodity level (production and consumption agreements[17]), the trade level (trade agreements[18]), and monetary cooperation (international monetary agreements[19]) are possible. In the regional competitive unit, there is competition at the commodity level for production and consumption initiative, the trade level for trade capacity, and the monetary level for monetary usage.

4.1.3 Perspectives on economic differences between regions

So what are healthy economic differences between regions? In common sense, this could be in the perspectives of space, time, and people. From a spatial point of view, regions should be able to solve their problems. To this end, a direction is needed to overcome the gap between areas.

In terms of time, economic differences between regions should be conducive to economic growth in the entire region. To this end, a healthy economic growth direction is needed.

Finally, from the people's point of view, each region must ensure that economic differences between people promote financial freedom. It must have a direction of value promotion toward people to do this.

4.2 What makes the difference in space overcome?

4.2.1 Perspective of space

Microeconomics assumes three kinds of participants: consumers, suppliers, and supervisors. And macroeconomics assumes governments (usually supervisors)[16], workers(usually consumers and suppliers)[20], companies (usually suppliers)[20], and foreign entities (usually consumers and suppliers)[20]. For markets to operate independently, the economic conditions for government intervention are important[21]. It is decided between market intervention in a broad sense and market intervention in a narrow sense.

In the broadest sense, market intervention means adequate government regulation and support for producers and consumers. It also refers to when the market operates autonomously without losing fairness despite the government's proper law and support to consumers and producers[22].

Narrow market intervention means minimizing government regulation and support to producers and consumers. It also refers to when markets operate autonomously without losing fairness despite minimal government regulation and support to consumers and producers[23].

If so, what is the direction beyond economic differences in space? This is the direction from autonomy in a narrow sense to independence in a broad sense.

4.2.2 Perspective of time

How do regional economic differences help overall regional economic growth? We can ask three different questions about local properties.

First, it is a question about the nature of the region. It is a question of which economic outputs will be traded for mutual benefit. Second, it is a question about the nature of time. It is a question of when economic output will be exchanged for mutual benefit. Finally, the third concerns interpersonal interests. This is a question of how economic output can be exchanged for mutual benefit.

What is the direction of healthy economic growth? Would it be cooperation or competition? This can be summarized in six questions.

If you are going to agree on cooperation, you need to discuss the items of commodity, trade, and currency. Regarding entities, we must decide where the economic output will be produced or consumed for mutual benefit. Regarding trading, it is up to you to decide which economic outcomes should be traded for mutual benefit. Finally, when it comes to money, you must choose which currency to use for the best mutual benefit.

Or, if you're trying to agree on competition, you have to discuss commodity, trade, or currency items. It would help if you decided where the economic output will be produced or consumed with entities. When trading, you must choose where to compete and trade economic output. As for currency, you have to decide which money to use.

4.2.3 Perspectives on economic differences between regions

This leaves two important questions.

First, how can regional economic differences promote human freedom? Money is a tool to express tradable utility. Market participants use currencies to conduct inter-market and intra-market transactions. Accordingly, economic growth refers to when the utility of society as a whole increases. And, in the direction of healthy economic growth, economic differences between regions are created to promote transactional financial freedom by people.

Second, how can economic differences between regions enhance human values? As for liberty, it can be said what not to do to promote human values. There is a difference between freedom and economic freedom. Humans are free, but financial freedom is only part of freedom.

There are two options for prioritizing economic freedom at the expense of other human freedom. One is collaboration only of economic liberty, which is not true freedom. The other is a dispute over financial independence, which is also not true freedom.

Therefore, human beings should not prioritize only economic freedom while reducing the sovereignty of other human beings. We do not collaborate only on economic liberty. This is not true freedom. We should not engage in conflicts solely of financial independence. This is also not true freedom.

5 Time – Difference in speed

5.1 How does economic growth happen?

5.1.1 Why should the economy grow?

What is Economic Growth? Simply put, economic growth refers to a situation in which the utility of society as a whole has increased[24]. So why should the economy grow? What are the critical factors for economic growth?

First, we need to look at how social utility is differentiated. Introducing a microeconomic perspective, we want to classify problems into three categories (as we have repeated so far). Some problems originate from space, problems that arise from time, and issues that stem from people.

There can be two positions on the question of origin in space. As demand progresses, the spatial situation within the region changes from the consumer's point of view. From the producer's point of view, as the supply moves, the spatial position within the region changes.

There can be two positions on the issue of time origin. Demand fluctuates over time as consumers progress their needs. As supply goes from the producer's point of view, supply fluctuates over time.

In matters of human origin, there can be two positions. From the consumer's point of view, as demand progresses, the position of supply and demand may change again. From the producer's point of view, as supply goes, the status of supply and demand may change again.

As a result, these issues extend to a macroeconomic perspective as well.

If we look at the problems originating from space, there can be four positions. As a government (usually a supervisor), it generates social utility by overseeing supply and demand for market space. Workers (mainly consumers and suppliers) generate social utility through the consumption of market space and the supply of labor goods. As a company (especially producers), it generates social utility by carrying out production activities based on demand in the market space. Finally, foreign actors (mainly consumers and suppliers) connect the market space and create social benefits through consumption and production.

If we look at the time issue, there can be four positions. As a government (usually a supervisor), social utility is generated by overseeing supply and demand within a given market time. Workers (mainly consumers and suppliers) generate social utility through the consumption of a given market time and the supply of labor goods. A company (especially producers) generates social utility by producing products based on demand within a given market time. Lastly, foreign actors (mainly consumers and suppliers) continue different market times and generate social utility through consumption and production.

If we look at the problems that originate from people, there can be four positions. As for governments (mainly supervisors), roles shift through agreeing on how to deal with the social benefits gained through supervision. As for workers (especially consumers and suppliers), their position changes as a process of maximizing social utility through the consumption done while considering the subsequent consumption. As for the company (mainly the producer), the position changes to maximize social utility through production while assessing the following manufacture. As for banks (especially companies with monetary specialty), the situation changes through how and how much they achieve the purpose of selling the financial products again to the subsequent earnings. Lastly, overseas actors (suppliers and consumers of beverages) change their position by maximizing the social benefits obtained by connecting different markets for the next production and consumption.

So why should the economy grow? It is not given as an obligation to each individual. But because it motivates action for the next better opportunity.

5.1.2 Origins of politics

The following factors are cultural factors for economic growth[25].

1. Less corruption

2. Securing property
3. Rule of Law
4. Better performance of public and private contracts
5. Developed financial system
6. Less murder
7. Government efficiency
8. Moderated inflation
9. Smooth circulation of capital
10. Free trade
11. Flexible exchange rate
12. Education

Less corruption actualizes possibility towards the next better opportunity[26].

As governments (mainly overseers), less political corruption allows them to be held in higher esteem and keep their political systems alive for the next opportunity. For workers (especially consumers and suppliers), reducing the cost of consuming behavior creates a more significant next opportunity. For businesses (mainly producers), lowering the cost of supplying activities creates the next more immense opportunity. For foreign actors (primarily consumers and producers), it induces a more excellent next opportunity to reduce costs for supply and demand actions.

Protecting property rights ensures action for the next better opportunity[27].

For governments (usually supervisors), it reduces property anxiety and increases the legitimacy of policies. As workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), it adds safety to demand behavior and further secures the next demand opportunity. As a business (primarily a producer), it adds security to your supply behavior and further ensures your next supply opportunity. For foreign actors (mainly consumers and producers), more robust property rights recognition than in other markets promotes participation in the next chance for that market.

The rule of law motivates the next better opportunity[28].

As the government (mainly the supervisor), it adds trust to the government itself, which increases the likelihood of the next opportunity. As workers (especially consumers and suppliers), it adds safety to demand behavior and further secures the next demand opportunity. As a business (mainly a producer), it protects your supply behavior and further ensures your next supply opportunity. For foreign actors (especially consumers and producers), a more robust perception of the rule of law than in other markets increases confidence and encourages re-engagement in the next opportunity.

Effective public and private contracts motivate the next better opportunity[29].

As the government (mainly the supervisor), it adds trust to the government itself, which increases the likelihood of the next opportunity. For workers (primarily consumers and suppliers), bottlenecks are reduced at each contract stage, leading to better opportunities. For firms (mainly producers), contractual production creates expectations for the next opportunity. Foreign actors (primarily consumers and producers) will find their next option in a relatively more efficient market.

A developed financial system empowers the next better opportunity[30].

As market confidence increases for governments (mainly supervisors), governments also generate persistence for the next opportunity. For workers (primarily

consumers and suppliers), it reduces transaction costs for capital when consuming, making it easier to participate in the market at the next opportunity. For firms (mainly producers), contractual production creates expectations for the next opportunity. Foreign actors (primarily consumers and producers) will find their next option in a relatively more efficient market.

A low murder rate motivates the next better opportunity[31].

As a government (mainly a supervisor), it is a way to promote the value of government and the continuity of government to raise expectations for the next opportunity. As workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), the added sense of safety during consumption motivates them to re-enter the market at the next opportunity. As a business (primarily a producer), the added sense of security during production will encourage them to re-enter the market at the next opportunity. For foreign actors (mainly consumers and producers), it increases confidence in justice and further motivates them to participate in the market at the next opportunity.

Government efficiency presents capacity for the next better opportunity[32].

As a government (mainly a supervisor), it is a way to promote the value of government and the continuity of government to raise expectations for the next opportunity. For workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), it would reduce the cost of anti-government and the burden on the next opportunity for consumption. For businesses (primarily producers), this would save them the expense of resentment against the government and reduce the load on the next opportunity in production. As for overseas entities (mainly consumers and producers), it can give them confidence that administrative costs can be minimized and motivates them to participate in the next market.

Moderate inflation motivates the next better opportunity[33].

As for the government (mainly the supervisor), the appropriate response of the value of money to price fluctuations increases the likelihood of the government's next opportunity. For workers (especially consumers and suppliers), it promotes continuous consumption by appropriately reflecting workers' wages according to price fluctuations. As a business (mainly a producer), it supports constant production opportunities by appropriately reflecting the company's sales in response to price fluctuations. For foreign actors (primarily consumers and producers), different exchange rates act as an attraction for market participation, further increasing the likelihood of a better next opportunity to participate in the market.

The smooth circulation of capital accomodates proficiency for the next better opportunity[34].

For governments (primarily supervisors), it avoids capital crunches, lowers social anxiety, and makes market participation opportunities more receptive. As workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), it provides the next opportunity to secure capital for consumption. As firms (primarily producers) generate more trade, they increase the market's viability and raise expectations for the next trading opportunity in production activities. For foreign actors (mainly consumers and producers), the difference in exchange rates according to capital acts as an attraction for market participation, motivating them to participate in the market at the next opportunity.

Free trade motivates the next better opportunity[35].

As the government (mainly the supervisor), it creates a constant opportunity in the market, giving the government the legitimacy to continue as the next opportunity. Workers (especially consumers and suppliers) promote more trade, increasing the viability of markets and creating expectations for the next trading opportunity needed for consumption behavior. As firms (primarily producers), they promote more trade, increasing the market viability and creating expectations for the next trading opportunity needed for productive action. Reducing transaction costs fur-

ther motivates foreign actors (mainly consumers and producers) to re-enter the market at the next opportunity.

A flexible exchange rate goes with a practice of the next better opportunity[36].

As governments (mainly supervisors), they add the legitimacy of the monetary value standard to the market, which increases the credibility of policies and, consequently, the continuity of government. As for workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), exchange rates reflect market conditions, which adds to their confidence in market transparency and makes them more amenable to participating in the next opportunity in consumption. As a business (producer), exchange rates reflect market conditions, adding confidence in market transparency and making production more amenable to participation in the next opportunity. For foreign actors (primarily consumers and producers), market conditions are more transparently reflected in exchange rates, making production and consumption more compliant to participate in the next opportunity.

Education motivates the next better opportunity[37].

As governments (primarily supervisors) by increasing market participants' understanding of the market, they become more engaged in market policy and thus more receptive to the following opportunities in policy-making. As workers (mainly consumers and suppliers), it enhances their understanding of consumption and heightens their expectations for the subsequent consumption opportunity. It improves supply understanding for businesses (primarily producers) and heightens expectations for the next supply opportunity. As for the foreign actors (mainly consumers and producers), the market offers them higher production and consumption possibilities, motivating them to participate in the market during the next opportunity.

The various discussions will continue, but with a minimum of common sense, it is clear that these are relevant to motivating the next better opportunity.

Accordingly, humans have tried to find the best way to harmonize these positions. And thus, liberal democracy was devised as the most advanced system.

Politics began to harmonize opinions among members of the economy[38]. And the liberal democracy[39] established on this basis has gone beyond its initial economic purpose and has become the standard for human decision-making. (Of course, there are exceptional cases specified by detailed legislation.)

5.1.3 How does economic growth happen?

Economic growth is obtained through maximizing opportunities at every moment in freedom. And politics was created to reconcile this, and as human beings, we are now following the standard of liberal democracy.

5.2 How to achieve healthy economic growth?

What is healthy economic growth in terms of opportunities? From the government's point of view, it is to pursue the best financial opportunity to have policy legitimacy. From the workers' perspective, it is to follow the best economic option and make the best consumption. From a business point of view, it is to pursue the best financial opportunity and produce the best product. From the perspective of foreign actors, it is to follow the best economic opportunities and achieve the best production and consumption.

But why do people have problems in real life when they pursue the best opportunities? Because opportunities are guaranteed, outcomes are not guaranteed. This comes down to a question of possibility. Differences in development add up, so even if options are insured, it becomes challenging to cooperate or compete in supply and demand.

So what is unhealthy economic growth? From an opportunity point of view, harmful economic growth is without minimal opportunity. But on the other hand, unhealthy economic growth in terms of outcomes is economic growth that occurs by reducing the value of the next opportunity.

5.2.1 What is healthy economic growth?

Thus, the logic for the conditions of unhealthy economic growth extends as follows. From the perspective of opportunity, it becomes a matter of the slightest opportunity. On the other hand, in terms of results, it becomes a matter of motivation through opportunities.

Accordingly, market indicators are needed. Throughout history, there has been an ongoing discussion about whether we should provide a minimum economic opportunity or increase the value of an economic opportunity. Giving minimum economic opportunities may undermine existing economic opportunities. Concentrating on the existing economic value may reduce the minimum financial chance.

Therefore, this is not an absolute issue but rather an issue that market supervisors must make an appropriate choice based on the current market situation. This is a problem that can be solved if the market supervision operation of liberal democracy is solid.

5.2.2 How can we make economic growth healthy?

6 Human – Way of understanding

6.1 How do people behave for free through capitalism?

6.1.1 How free are people?

What kind of being is a human being? Humans are free beings[40].

What is human's ultimate freedom? Ultimate freedom means the same freedom to have rights and duties[41].

What are your rights and responsibilities? A right means something granted to exercise a subject's attributes. An obligation is a compulsion to exercise the features of an issue within their ability.

What is the law [42]? Humans are social beings. Laws are human rights and obligations defined through social agreements.

Why should we obey the law? Human beings are social beings and must abide by the law for the survival of society.

What does the law enforce? For the continuation of society, each individual's freedom is enforced up to the limits set by law.

What is law in a liberal democracy? In a liberal democracy, a social consensus is sought in a free and democratic way to set human rights and duties into law.

How accessible are people in a liberal democracy? People are free to the extent that they can have the rights and obligations set forth by the law agreed upon based on liberal democracy.

6.1.2 What kind of existence is humanity in a capitalist society?

How does capitalism based on liberal democracy define people? From the point of view of capitalism based on liberal democracy, individuals can have specific attributes such as rights and duties. Here, "specific attributes" are more specifically defined by law.

How is ownership classified from the point of view of capitalism based on liberal democracy? In capitalism based on liberal democracy, the economic entities that can claim ownership are classified in the broadest range into domestic and foreign individuals, domestic and foreign companies, and domestic and foreign governments[43]. In addition, exceptional cases such as NGOs (Non-Governmental Organizations) are regulated in more detail by law[43]. Accordingly, in capitalism based on liberal democracy, people are free as much as the law stipulates.

6.1.3 How do people become free through capitalism?

Why do people feel limited in their freedom? This is because it is difficult for people to reach happiness only with the space the law prescribes. Accordingly, people must repeatedly redefine their rights and obligations in society. And this leads people to happiness.

Then, in conclusion, how does a person become free from capitalism based on liberal democracy? Human society has expanded human freedom by constantly discussing opportunities for social continuation. And through this, human beings get happiness.

6.2 How to promote human values through capitalism?

6.2.1 What are human values?

How does value arise? There are two aspects[44][45]. One is social value. It is an arithmetic value and occurs through the market. Another is personal values. This is a subjective value determined by individuals' perceptions.

What value do people have? Accordingly, it has an arithmetic value and an intrinsic value. What arithmetic value do humans have? This includes property and labor[46]. What are the inherent values of human beings? This includes having the same freedom to have rights and obligations.

Then how can a person's nonarithmetic intrinsic value be defined? It is the individual's sense of the same freedom to have rights and duties as a subjective value.

6.2.2 How to promote human values?

What do people live for? People live for happiness[47].

How is a human arithmetic value converted into happiness? Happiness is a subjective concept and is defined by human intrinsic values. Accordingly, arithmetic values are affected by human inherent values.

How is a person's intrinsic value converted into happiness? Human's inherent joy is being equally free to have rights and duties.

Then, how should the value of people be promoted in capitalism based on liberal democracy? We need to provide the freedom of equal opportunity to have the rights and obligations of the arithmetic value of work and possession based on the inherent happiness of human beings. Through this, people realize joy through their own free will.

6.3 What is human rights?

Human rights are the rights that allow a person to recognize himself as a human being. It is essential for the survival of human society.

What is the relationship between human rights, the economy, and welfare? The integrity of human rights refers to the ultimate pursuit and goal of the right economy and proper interest. Accordingly, the right to be free from all problems that may arise according to the aspect of human existence is called human rights.

6.3.1 Why does the problem occur?

Why does a situation arise in which people are not free from all possible problems depending on the mode of their existence? This is because the differences in their aspects of existence were understood as discrimination against their aspects of reality. What is the difference? Differences arise when the attributes expressing fact are not identical.

Is there a being without a difference? All beings change. Therefore, everything that exists is unique.

What is Discrimination? Human is a social being. Recognizing differences between social groups as a violent perception is called discrimination.

If so, is discrimination based on difference justified? No, it causes problems in society. If so, is it justified to recognize discrimination only as an individual problem? No, it underestimates the fundamental reasons for solving society's problems.

6.3.2 How should human rights issues be addressed?

How does difference become discrimination? Discrimination arises from a violent perception of differences between social groups.

There are two types of human rights issues. One is tolerating violent awareness, and the other is participating in fierce understanding.

Why does society condone violent perceptions? When members of the community judge that a problem is unrelated to their well-being, they are likely to favor violent perceptions. Why does society become violently involved in damaging awareness? When members of the community judge that a problem gives them distorted happiness, they are likely to engage in violent cognition.

How should human rights be addressed under a liberal democracy? In terms of violence, it responds as a violation of human rights law. Judging by the judgment of members of society, we are obliged by law to respect the reasonable values cherished by unique community members, not just a part of it.

6.3.3 Human rights to all-human obligation

As discussed earlier, human rights are the rights that enable people to recognize themselves as people. It is essential for the survival of human society. Accordingly, human rights can have problems in two parts. One is about cognition; the other is about being human.

Regarding cognition, we already know that every individual has a unique value. However, since this is a perception from the perspective of seeing humanity as a whole, irrational errors in judgment may occur if a conflict of opinions occurs.

Also, since human rights are based on human existence, any deterioration of human existence as a whole is likely to undermine the purest meaning of human rights.

Therefore, if we see human rights as a basis of duty, as human beings, we must promote the rights of all humans for human reason and existence.

6.4 The significance and commonalities of religion

What is religion in society? Religion is a method that transcends human reason and seeks to solve the problems of the world.

Is religion superfluous in society? This question is impossible to answer. Denying faith in the community regarding human rights is irrational in that many people have beliefs beyond human reason[48]. Because human civilization has always had problems in one way or another, and if there is an existence beyond human reason, this can only be answered through religion.

6.4.1 Relationship between society and religion

Is religion essential to society? Religion must contribute by example and helping in matters indispensable to society.

But aren't there times when religion causes social problems? There are times when this happens, but regarding human rights; it should not be seen as a cause of religion. Faith becomes a problem in society when it becomes violent.

But what if, as human beings, religion creates an argument that encourages violence? The ultimate goal of all religions is peace and salvation. Therefore, they must convince society before being criticized for their violence.

How can religion persuade society? Their ultimate goal is to try to convince others by setting an example of peace and salvation in the community.

6.4.2 About violent religion

As human beings, what should we do when religion gives up persuasion and shows violence to society? Following their priority of peace and salvation of men, we can ask them to set an example here and now.

What if their religion refuses to comply with these legitimate requests? This is religious violence and should be regulated by the laws of society.

6.5 About the decision of death

6.5.1 About legal death

Can we, as humans, understand everything about life? No. As humans, we cannot know everything. So, is forced death by law reasonable? If you follow a religion that transcends logic, this is a matter that religion must persuade by setting an example to society. On the other hand, if you follow the reason, it can be established that there are no irrational premises for death according to the law.

What examples can be given of death by law? A prime example is the death penalty, which is still debated. What irrational thinking should be excluded when determining death by law? Foolish things must be excluded from all aspects and regulated by law as a social agreement.

6.5.2 About death by law that excludes irrationality

What kind of irrationality should be excluded from death by law? This refers to the irrationality that humans can make while making choices. Can human knowledge objectively examine irrational decisions? This can be cataloged by examining the premises of game theory developed to date.

6.5.3 Considerations to avoid legal decisions on unreasonable deaths that illustrate abortion rights

1. (Extended Game Theory Law 1) Market participants minimize irrational judgments to maximize rational judgments.
 - People involved in abortion judgments should minimize irrational judgments to maximize rational judgments.
2. (Extended Game Theory Rule 2) Market participants are influenced by whether they play games simultaneously or sequentially.
 - An abortion situation is a decision-making in which the mother's decision affects the child's position. Accordingly, it is necessary to look not only at the mother's decision but also at whether it was reasonable for the child to abort the child after the mother gave birth.
3. (Extended Game Theory Law 3) The less you know about the market, the more mistakes you make before making sound decisions.
 - Decision whether or not to have an abortion should be made assuming that the mother's and child's information after childbirth are at the same level.
4. (Extended Game Theory Law 4) Any decision can have multiple meanings.
 - The decision to abort a child should never have any motive other than a reasonable one that can be fully agreed upon.
5. (Extended Game Theory Law 5) Larger marginal utility can be created due to something not considered during the market transaction.
 - When a mother decides to have an abortion, she should not have an abortion because there are facts she should hide or facts the child should not know.
6. (Extended Game Theory Law 6) Market participants may prefer a one-time opportunity over a trade based on probability calculations.
 - When deciding to have an abortion, the underlying reason must be moral, and abortion should not be simply for probabilistic reasons.
7. (Extended Game Theory Law 7) Market participants may mistake themselves for rationality and make poor decisions.
 - When deciding to have an abortion, it must be assumed that an irrational decision could harm the mother and child.
8. (Extended Game Theory Law 8) Even if you try to make decisions with everyone in mind, there will always be internal differences in the distribution of benefits among game players.
 - When deciding on an abortion, the positions of everyone involved other than the mother and the postpartum child must be considered comprehensively.

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